
Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic **FLEX**ibility
services in the distribution **GRID**

FLEXIGRID's Visual Materials and Identity Set Deliverable 9.5 WP9

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Approvals

	Company
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ABBREVIATIONS

PC: Project Coordinator

CA: Consortium Agreement

CC: Communication Committee

DoA: Description of Action

EC: European Commission

GA: General Assembly

IPR: Intellectual Property Right

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

M: Month

PH: Project Handbook

R&D: Research and Development

SC: Steering Committee

TP: Technical Partner

WP: Work Package

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

DMP: Data Management Plan

H2020: Horizon 2020

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1. INTRODUCTION

This manual serves as a guide for the identification and visual communication of FLEXIGRID.

It includes the identity of the brand, the versions, colours, fonts and applications that should not vary in any case.

It is recommended to always use the high-quality version for printed documents and the screen version for digital documents.

The idea of FLEXIGRID logo came up with three main concepts: Flexible, Reliable and Distribution in order to obtain an impressive and memorable symbol expressing, summarizing and giving visual image and essence to these three words applied to smart grids.

Also shown are materials that can be made in the future. Some of the materials shown are examples and will be adapted according to the objectives and the context in which they are to be used.

2. VISUAL IDENTITY

2.1. Logotype Size

If the logo does not include the caption, it can be included up to a minimum of 2 centimetres wide to ensure its correct display, and the height will be proportional.

If the logo does not include the caption, it can be included up to a minimum of 4,5 centimetres wide to ensure its correct display, and the height will be proportional.

Figure 1. FLEXIGRID Logo size and exclusion zone

2.2. Logotype colour version

Below are shown the colours defined for the brand and the percentages and codes for the different variations of graphical reproductions.

Figure 2. FLEXIGRID Brand Identity

2.3. Logotype black & white (positive and negative) versions

The brand may be used mainly in four colours. For those applications where it is not possible to use four-colours, other options in black & white one ink have been defined.

Figure 3. FLEXIGRID Black and white logo and greyscale versions

2.4. Fonts

The following font has been used to build the brand: NORWEST

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECR
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULL,**

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQ
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMM**

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQUAM NULLA. SUSPENSISSE EGESTAS LE
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMMODO, DIAM LECTUS LOBORTIS VELIT, AT**

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQUAM NULLA. S
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMMODO, DIAM LEC**

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQUAM NULLA. SUSPENSISSE EGESTAS LECTUS
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMMODO, DIAM LECTUS LOBORTIS VELIT, AT
IMPERDIE MAURIS NISI AT SEM. SED IACULIS VEHICULA URINA AT RHONCUS. VESTIBULUM LEO TORTOR, VESTIBULUM VEL**

**LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQUAM NULLA. SUSPENSISSE EGESTAS LECTUS
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMMODO, DIAM LECTUS LOBORTIS VELIT, AT
IMPERDIE MAURIS NISI AT SEM. SED IACULIS VEHICULA URINA AT RHONCUS. VESTIBULUM LEO TORTOR, VESTIBULUM VEL
FAUCIBUS EU. ADIPISCING VEL LOREM, CNAIS YITAE TURPIS MI. DUIS DIGNISSIM CONSEQUAT MAINA NEZ POSSERE. NULLA**

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECTETUR ADIPISCING ELIT. DUIS VEL ALIQUAM NULLA. SUSPENSISSE EGESTAS LECTUS
GRAVIDA DUI CONSEQUAT IACULIS. NULLA ULTRICIES, TORTOR ET SAGITTIS COMMODO, DIAM LECTUS LOBORTIS VELIT, AT
IMPERDIE MAURIS NISI AT SEM. SED IACULIS VEHICULA URINA AT RHONCUS. VESTIBULUM LEO TORTOR, VESTIBULUM VEL
FAUCIBUS EU. ADIPISCING VEL LOREM, CNAIS YITAE TURPIS MI. DUIS DIGNISSIM CONSEQUAT MAINA NEZ POSSERE. NULLA

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FAUCIBUS EU. ADIPISCING VEL LOREM, CNAIS YITAE TURPIS MI. DUIS DIGNISSIM CONSEQUAT MAINA NEZ POSSERE. NULLA

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FAUCIBUS EU. ADIPISCING VEL LOREM, CNAIS YITAE TURPIS MI. DUIS DIGNISSIM CONSEQUAT MAINA NEZ POSSERE. NULLA

Figure 4. FLEXIGRID Logo's fonts

3. BRAND IDENTITY

3.1. Official templates

Poster

Reproduction Poster in mockup. Real size A1

Figure 5. FLEXIGRID Poster Sample

Minutes Template

Reproduction minutes template for FLEXIGRID meetings in mockup

Figure 6. FLEXIGRID Minutes Template

Agenda Template

Reproduction agenda template for FLEXIGRID events in mockup

Figure 7. FLEXIGRID Agenda Template

List of attendees

Reproduction list attendees in FLEXIGRID events in mockup

Figure 8. FLEXIGRID List of attendees

General Presentation

General presentation of the project and template for presentations within the framework of the FLEXIGRID project

<p>1</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>6</p>

Figure 9. FLEXIGRID General Presentation

Office Material

Example of office equipment that could be produced during project implementation if deemed necessary for the project's dissemination activity

Figure 10. FLEXIGRID Office Material

3.2. Events Materials

During the project, an information brochure will be produced to disseminate the objectives and results of the project at events and meetings, as well as a roll-up to decorate stages, stands or any other place where FLEXIGRID.

The reproduction of badges has been made as an example of corporate material for events.

Figure 11. FLEXIGRID Events Material

3.3. Merchandising

During the four years of the project different merchandising and image materials will be made. As an example, folders and mugs have been reproduced. These materials will be defined throughout the project according to the context in which they will be used

Figure 13. FLEXIGRID Merchandising

4. RULES FOR INCLUDING THE CONSORTIUM LOGOS

Partners' logos should always be included in FLEXIGRID's official documents and graphics according to the following rules:

- ✓ **Posters:** must be included at the end of the design.
- ✓ **Brochures or flyers or printed documents:** may be included on the front or back cover, depending on the design
- ✓ **Power Point presentations or similar:** to be included on the first or last slide.
- ✓ **Other documents** which may include, but are not required to include
- ✓ **Official document templates (agenda, minutes, list of attendees, etc):** to include them, a specific cover should be made with the title of the document, in the context in which it is made and the set of logos. It will never go in the footer. The footer is reserved for the Acknowledgment of EU funding and Disclaimer.
- ✓ **Merchandising materials (folders, event materials, objects, etc):** may be included provided that adequate visibility is ensured.